

A Survey of Contribution from Indian Laboratories to Plant Chemistry*

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I feel deeply honoured for having been asked to deliver the Acharya P. C. Ray Memorial Lecture. Acharya Ray is rightly considered as the Father of Chemistry in India. My own teacher Professor Biman Bihari Dey, the distinguished organic chemist was one of his early students. I still remember vividly Acharya Ray's visit to Presidency College, Madras where his student Dr. Dey was Professor. His simplicity, directness and intense love for India were all too evident. Acharya Ray's students spread out far and wide and were the pioneers of chemical education and research in India.

The chemical investigation of plants has been a favourite area of research in India for several decades. Situated as it is in the tropical and sub-tropical belts of the world, India is endowed with a profusion of plant life numbering some 20,000 species. One of the earliest, if not the first to work on plant products was Sir John Lionel Simonsen¹ who served at Presidency College, Madras, Forest Research Institute, Dehra Dun and at the Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore before returning to England. His discovery that Δ^8 -carene was the major constituent of Indian turpentine and his isolation of longifolene from *Pinus longifolia* were important achievements. It is well known that longifolene has been the subject of outstanding chemical and mechanistic work by Dr. Sukh Dev in India and also by many other distinguished organic chemists in other countries for several decades.

Another great pioneer in the chemical work on plants was Professor S. Siddiqui, who investigated in the early years many plants of medicinal or economic importance. His work on *Rauwolfia serpentina* along with the clinical work of Dr. R. J. Vakil triggered off the world-wide search for medicinal agents from plants, after the Second World War. The late Prof. T. R. Seshadri² at Andhra and Delhi Universities and Prof. K. Venkataraman³ at Bombay University and later at the National Chemical Laboratory, Poona have carried out extensive studies on oxygen heterocycles, by way of isolation from plants, structure determination and syntheses which have won international recognition.

The amount of chemical work on plants carried out in India is prodigious. Some of the highlights from this massive output, particularly work carried

out during the last fifteen years, which have an element of novelty on a classification according to structural types are presented in this lecture.

Alkaloids :

The medicinal importance of the genus *Piper* has led to examination of several of its species⁴. Joshi and coworkers isolated from *Piper trichostachyon* C.D.C. four new alkaloids piperstachine(I), cyclostachine A(II), cyclostachine B(III) and cyclopiperstachine(IV). The structures were elucidated by a combination of chemical and spectroscopic methods and confirmed by syntheses⁵.

Confirmation of the structure of cyclostachine A was obtained by X-ray analysis⁶. Cyclostachines A and B evidently arise by an internal Diels-Alder reaction of the amide(V) and cyclopiperstachine from piperstachine. The *cyclo*-compounds are not artefacts but exist in the plant. The genus *Crotalaria* is known to produce macrocyclic ester alkaloids incorporating a pyrrolizidine system. Atal *et al* have investigated a large number of plants of the genus occurring in the Jammu region and isolated over a dozen new alkaloids⁷. Cromadurine (VI) is a typical alkaloid of the group⁸.

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The genus *Ancistrocladaceae* is represented only by one species in India, *Ancistrocladus heyneanus* Wall. A novel group of isoquinoline alkaloids has been isolated from this species. The major alkaloid ancistrocladine has been assigned the structure and stereochemistry depicted in VII. The chemistry of this group of alkaloids has been reviewed recently⁹.

VI

VII

From *Tiliacora racemosa* Colebr. (Menispermaceae) a number of bis-benzylisoquinoline alkaloids were isolated, which are unique in having the isoquinoline moieties joined through a diphenyl unit and not through a diphenyl ether unit as is common. Essential features of the structures of tiliacorine and the accompanying alkaloids were established some years ago¹⁰. It was only recently that the position of the phenolic hydroxyl group could be established¹¹. Bhakuni *et al* have established the absolute configuration of tiliacorine, in a unique manner, using biosynthesis as a tool¹², permitting its depiction as VIII.

More than a dozen alkaloids have been isolated by Bhakuni *et al* from *Cocculus laurifolius* DC and their structures elucidated¹³. Of the isolated bases isococculidine (IX) is a neuromuscular blocking agent.

VIII

IX

Six bases of the bis-benzylisoquinoline type were isolated from *Cocculus pendulus* Forsk by Bhakuni *et al* and characterised¹⁴. Of these bases cocculinine (X) showed activity against human epidermoid carcinoma of the nasopharynx in tissue culture at a concentration of 4.7 µg/ml.

X

From the leaves of *Murraya koenigii* Spreng, used as a flavouring material for many items of food, almost thirty alkaloids belonging to the carbazole group have been isolated. Chakraborty *et al* were the first to report the isolation of the alkaloids girinimbine, mahanimbine and murrayacine¹⁵. Subsequently, a number of other alkaloids were isolated by other laboratories and there is confusion due to the multiplicity of names given to the same alkaloid. Mahanimbine was correctly formulated as XI¹⁶, girinimbine as XII¹⁷, murrayacine as XIII¹⁸, koenimbine as XIV¹⁹ and koenimbidine as XV¹⁶. Isomahanimbine is a position isomer of mahanimbine with the structure XVI, mahanine was formulated as XVII²⁰.

XI R₁ = Me; R₂ = H XII R₁ = Me, R₂, R₃ = H, R₄ = Me

XVI R₁ = H, R₂ = Me XIII R₁ = OH, R₂, R₃ = H; R₄ = Me

XIV R₁ = Me, R₂ = OMe; R₃ = H; R₄ = Me

XV R₁ = Me; R₂, R₃ = OMe; R₄ = Me

XVII R₁ = Me; R₂ = H, R₃ = OH,

Among the more complex alkaloids, cyclo-mahanimbine appears correctly constituted as XVIII²¹. An X-ray study of murrayazoline (mahanimbidine) has confirmed the structure as XIX²². It has been suggested²³ that bicyclo-mahanimbine and bicyclomahanimbicine may have structures XX and XXI rather than XXII and XXIII originally proposed²⁴.

XVIII

XIX

XX $R_1 = \text{Me}; R_2 = \text{H}$ XXII $R_1 = \text{Me}; R_2 = \text{H}$
 XXI $R_1 = \text{H}; R_2 = \text{Me}$ XXIII $R_1 = \text{H}; R_2 = \text{Me}$

The chemistry of carbazole alkaloids from *M. koenigii*, as well as from other plants of the *Rutaceae* has been the subject of two recent reviews^{25, 26}. From the leaves of *Tylophora asthmatica* Wight et Arn. used in folk medicine as a cure for asthma several phenanthroindolizidine alkaloids, tylophorine(XXIV), tylophorinine(XXV), tylophorinidine(XXVI), d-isotylocrebrine(XXVII) and the *seco* alkaloid septicine (XXVIII) have been isolated. All aspects of the structure and stereochemistry of these alkaloids have been established. Two recent reviews give a detailed account of the chemistry of this group^{27, 28}.

XXIV $R = \text{OMe}; \beta\text{-H at } C^{13a}$
 $R_1 = \text{Me} \quad R_2 = \text{OH}$
 XXV $R = \text{H}; \alpha\text{-H at } C^{13a}$
 $R_1 = \text{Me} \quad R_2 = \text{OH}$
 XXVI $R = \text{H} \quad \beta\text{-H at } C^{13a}$
 $R_1 = \text{H} \quad R_2 = \text{OH}$
 XXVII
 XXVIII

Clinical trials conducted by Shivpuri²⁹ with the total alkaloids of *Tylophora asthmatica* as well as pure tylophorine appear to support the common belief of the beneficial effects of the leaves in treating asthma and allergic rhinitis. All the phenanthroindolizidine alkaloids show significant anti-cancer activity³⁰.

The Department of Pure Chemistry, Calcutta University has been very active in the field of indole

alkaloids under the leadership of Professor Asima Chatterjee during the past three decades. More than a hundred species of plants, a large number belonging to *Apocyanaceae* have been screened for alkaloids and about forty new bases have been reported.

A recent review³¹ has dealt with the many interesting alkaloids isolated from *Alstonia scholaris* R. Br. The isolation and structure elucidation (X-ray) of nareline(XXIX) isolated from this plant is of great interest. This has the novel 2-azaadamantane skeleton³².

XXIX Nareline

XXX: $C_8 - \beta\text{-H}$
 XXXI: $O_8 - \alpha\text{-H}$

The alkaloids venenatine and isovenenatine were first isolated from *Alstonia venenata* R. Br. and assigned structures XXX and XXXI on the basis of degradation studies³³.

The hypotensive activity of the extracts of the plant was shown to be due to the presence of reserpine. In an admirably thorough study of all parts of *Alstonia venenata*, Chatterjee *et al* have reported the isolation and structure elucidation of twenty other alkaloids, in addition to the above. Broadly, the alkaloids belong to the yohimbine, aspidofractinine and vincadifformine types. The occurrence of the mono-terpenoid, venoterpine, is of great biogenetic significance. The chemistry of the alkaloids of *Alstonia venenata* has been the subject of a recent review³⁴. The structure of the very complex bis-indoline alkaloid amataine (grandifoline) (XXXII) isolated from *Voacanga grandifolia* Miq. was solved in a multi-national effort³⁵.

XXXII

XXXIII

Isodihydrocadambine, isolated through an elaborate purification procedure from extracts of *Anthocephalus cadamba* Miq. was shown to have structure XXXIII. It has a novel structure incorporating a N_4-C_{10} bond³⁰.

It is of interest that camptothecin, the much sought-after anti-cancer alkaloid was isolated from *Mappia foetida* Miers in yields of more than 0.1 per cent (cf. 0.005 per cent from *Camptotheca acuminata*), along with minor alkaloids 9-methoxy-camptothecin and mappicine^{37,38}.

Biosynthetic and tissue culture studies on alkaloids :

Excellent work has been done for the first time in India, on the biosynthesis of several important alkaloids by Bhakuni and Kapil at the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. Specific incorporation of (+)-reticuline (XXXIV) into boldine(XXXV) was demonstrated in *Litsea glutinosa*. The evidence supports the direct oxidative coupling of (+)-reticuline to isoboldine(XXXVI) which in turn was a specific precursor for boldine^{8,9}.

XXXIV

XXXV $R_1 = R_2 = R_4 = Me$

$R_3 = R_5 = H$

XXXVI $R_1 = R_2 = R_4 = Me$

$R_3 = R_5 = H$

The biosynthesis of papaverine⁴⁰, of the bis-benzylisoquinoline alkaloid cocculinin⁴¹ of the abnormal Erythrina alkaloids cocculidine and cocculine⁴², the morphinandienone alkaloid sebiferine⁴³ and several others have all been worked out by Bhakuni and coworkers.

Very interesting tissue culture studies on alkaloid-bearing plants such as *Atropa belladonna* and *Tylophora asthmatica* have been carried out by Chadha *et al* at Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Bombay which shed light on the stage of formation of alkaloids in these plants⁴⁴.

Oxygen heterocycles :

A systematic examination of plants belonging to the *Umbelliferae* occurring in the Himalayan region has led to the isolation of a large number of new coumarins. Typical compounds are heratomin (XXXVII) from *Heracleum thomsonii* and sesebrinol (XXXVIII) from *Seseli sibiricum*⁴⁵.

XXXVII

XXXVIII

Many plants belonging to the *Rutaceae* and *Guttiferae* have been examined giving interesting new coumarins. Morellin, isolated from the seeds of *Garcinia morella* Desr. is a modified xanthone of very complex structure(XXXIX) resolved by X-ray analysis⁴⁶.

XXXIX

The structure of the complex oxygen heterocyclic xanthochymol(XL) from *Garcinia xanthochymus* was determined by X-ray analysis of the dibrosylate of its isomerisation product isoxanthohymol⁴⁷. It is most interesting that cambogin, from *G. cambogia* is enantiomeric with isoxanthochymol⁴⁸.

XL

Among unusual flavonoids isolated recently are cycloheterophyllin(XLI)⁴⁹ from *Artocarpus heterophyllus* Lamk, chaplashin(XLII)⁵⁰ from *Artocarpus chaplasha* Roxb. and cyclointegrin(XLIII)⁵¹ from *Artocarpus integer* Thunb.

XLI

XLII

XI.III

Terpenoids :

Important contributions have been made in the field of terpenoids mainly due to the work of the schools of research led by Prof. S. C. Bhattacharyya and Dr. Sukh Dev. A large number of the economically important essential oils and resin exudates have been examined by these groups over the past three decades. Over a hundred new compounds belonging to the sesqui-, di- and tri-terpenoid groups have been isolated, many of them of novel types.

From fungus-infected agarwood, *Aquillaria agallocha* Roxb. agarospirol(XLIV), α - and β -agarofurans(XLV, XLVI) and dihydroagarofuran were isolated and structurally characterised⁵².

XLIV

XLV

XLVI

Costus root oil (*Sassaurea lappa* Clarke) has been intensively studied by the Bhattacharyya group and several sesquiterpenes with the germacrane skeleton have been isolated and characterised. Typical studies are the structure elucidation of dehydrocostuslactone(XLVII)⁵³ and the transformation products of costunolide(XLVIII)⁵⁴.

XLVII

XLVIII

(+)-Junenol(XLIX), canarone(L) and epikhusinal(LI) were isolated from Indian black dammar resin (*Canarium strictum* Roxb.)⁵⁵.

XLIX

L

LI

The structure of β -bergamotene(LII), a novel sesquiterpene was determined⁵⁶.

LII

The constituents of North Indian vetiver oil were shown to be distinctly different from those of the oil obtained from other parts of the country, which contain essentially alpha and beta vetivones and related compounds. The former is conspicuous by the presence of many antipodal cadinenic and eudesmanic compounds. The major constituent is khusinol(LIII)⁵⁷. Another biogenetically significant constituent is khusiol(LIV), which is perhaps a precursor of the zizaene type of sesquiterpenes⁵⁸.

LIII

LIV

From *Cedrus deodara* Loud. several hydrocarbons and alcohols were isolated. Typical compounds are alpha and beta himachalenes(LV, LVI)⁵⁹, himachalol(LVII)⁶⁰ and allohimachalol(LVIII)⁶¹.

LV

LVI

LVII

LVIII

Humulene (alpha-, LIX) zerumbone(LX), caryophyllene and curcumene were some of the constituents of *Zingiber zerumbet* Smith and all aspects of the structure of the first two compounds were elucidated⁶².

LIX R=CH₃
LX R=O

The chemistry of isolongifolene(LXI) has been studied in detail⁶³.

LXI

LXII

The first tetracyclic sesquiterpene longicyclene (LXII) was also found to be of natural occurrence⁶⁴. Ishwarane(LXIII) and ishwarone(LXIV) are the other rare tetracyclic sesquiterpenes whose structures have been completely elucidated⁶⁵.

LXIII R=OH,
LXIV R=O

LXV

A number of germacranolides were isolated from *Tithonia tagetiflora* Desf. of which tagitinin F displayed significant anti-cancer activity(LXV)⁶⁶.

Several diterpenes have been isolated from *Coleus forskohlii* Brig.⁶⁷ of which the most interesting is coleonol(LXVI) possessing hypotensive and spasmolytic activities.

From the resin exudate of *Commiphora mukul* Hook. ex Stocks used in Indian medicine as an anti-inflammatory agent several compounds were isolated such as cembrene-A and mukulol(LXVII) whose structures were determined⁶⁸.

LXVI

LXVII

The anti-inflammatory properties are however due to the steroid fraction from which three new

steroids guggulsterol-I, guggulsterol-II and guggulsterol-III which are formulated as LXVIII, LXIX and LXX⁶⁹ have been isolated.

LXVIII R=OH
LXX R=H

LXIX

Hardwickic acid(LXXI) isolated from the oleoresin of *Hardwickia pinnata* Roxb. is the first simple member of the rearranged labdanes⁷⁰.

LXXI

Cheilanthatriol(LXXII) from the fern *Cheilanthes farinosa*-Kaulf. belongs to the rare group of sesterterpenoids⁷¹.

LXXII

Typical of the large number of triterpenoids which have been isolated and characterised are the

19-oxygenated oleanane arjunic acid (*Terminalia arjuna* W and A) (LXXIII)⁷³, the hopane mollugenol-A (*Mollugo hirta* Roxb.) (LXXIV)⁷³, the ursane lactic acid (*Lantana camara* Linn.) (LXXV)⁷⁴, etc.

Litsomentol, is the simplest member of the cucurbitacin group (LXXVI)⁷⁵ and is exceedingly toxic. Vilasinin, from the leaves of *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss belongs to the interesting group of tetranortriterpenoids (LXXVII)⁷⁶.

Malabaricol (LXXVIII) isolated from *Ailanthus malabarica* represents a new fundamental type of triterpene not encountered before⁷⁷.

Glycosides :

A few glycosides with interesting biological activity will be discussed.

From the leaves of *Cleistanthus collinus* (Roxb.) Benth. and Hook. cleistanthin (LXXIX) was isolated along with some other lignans⁷⁸.

Cleistanthin induces significant increase in neutrophilic granulocyte count in many species of animals.

From the reputed medicinal plant *Picrorhiza kurrooa* Benth. two C₉ iridoid glycosides picroside I (LXXX) and kutkoside (LXXXI) were isolated and their structures determined⁷⁹. Kutkin, which is a stable mixed crystal of these two glycosides shows weak diuretic activity⁷⁹.

Examination of *Asclepias curassavica* Linn. collected from Dehra Dun yielded results differing from the plant of Brazilian origin⁸⁰. The principal glycoside asclepin (LXXXII) showed excellent cardiotoxic activity similar to that of digoxin, with a lower cumulative toxicity.

The cardiac glycoside peruvoside (LXXXIII) was isolated from *Thevetia nerifolia* Juss. and its structure was established⁸¹. Extensive biological work has been done on peruvoside both in India and in Germany. The compound has undergone extensive clinical trials and has been introduced

LXXX R=H, K'=Cinnamoyl

LXXXI R=Vanilloyl, R'=H

LXXXII

under the trade name 'Encordin'. It compares very favourably with digoxin.

LXXXIII

It has been possible to present only a few selected items from the extensive work carried out in India on the chemistry of plant products. It is regrettable that there has been a decline in the activity in this area during the past few years. There is still an enormous amount of work waiting to be done, using comparatively new tools such as preparative high performance liquid chromatography. Aided by spectroscopic methods, it should be possible to uncover many more fundamental structural types not encountered earlier. It would

also be advisable to design more rational procedures for the discovery of drugs, fertility control agents, insect control agents etc from the plant kingdom. The neem tree *Azadirachta indica* grows extensively all over the plains of India. But it is in West Germany that a Neem Tree Research and Development Programme is being set up²².

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